

THERMAL STABILITY OF COPPER BASE NANOPHASE COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

Nanophase multilayered copper base composites were evaluated in terms of their elevated temperature thermal stability. The nanophase composites consist of a copper matrix that contains a second insoluble phase such as molybdenum or niobium. The volume fraction second phase was 15%. The materials were produced using a codeposition or alternate layer physical vapor deposition process. Room temperature tensile tests indicated that the strength of the copper base materials was enhanced with the nanostructure morphology. The room temperature tensile strength of the nanophase composites was found to be proportional to the inverse square root of the copper layer thickness (Hall-Petch relationship). The nanophase composites were aged at 590°, 650°, and 700°C (1100°, 1200° and 1300°F). Microhardness measurements indicated that the initially rapid softening rate decayed to a much slower rate after a few hours at temperature. This thermal aging effect was found to be attributed to the molybdenum layers pinching off and agglomerating.

KEYWORDS: Nanophase, Copper, Composite, Thermal Stability,
Physical Vapor Deposition, Multilayer

1. INTRODUCTION

As the performance requirements increase for aerospace structures, greater demands are placed on the materials of construction. In actively cooled structures, materials are required to have a unique combination of high strength and excellent thermal conductivity. For example, copper base alloys have been successfully used in the regeneratively cooled combustion chamber of the liquid propellant rocket engines that power the Space Shuttle Orbiter. Copper base nanostructure composites are candidate materials for future high-temperature, actively cooled structures. Their

unique nanometer scale microstructure has been projected to enhance mechanical and thermophysical properties compared to conventional crystalline materials.¹ This fine scale also brings with it concern for the thermal stability of these materials. It is the purpose of this paper to address the thermal aging behavior of copper base nanophase composites. The materials were a two-phase mixture of copper and a second insoluble phase (which was either molybdenum or niobium). The materials were produced by electron beam physical vapor deposition (PVD). Two copper nanophase composites were evaluated: Cu-15v/oMo and Cu-15v/oNb.

2. EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

Samples of Cu-15v/oMo and Cu-15v/oNb were produced by electron beam PVD. Sample deposition runs were made with either alternating fluxes of copper and molybdenum or niobium or with simultaneous deposition of copper and molybdenum or niobium. Deposition was controlled to produce varied interlayer spacings with 15 volume percent of molybdenum or niobium.

The method of coevaporation calls for the production of different metal vapors from two or more sources. This approach to depositing metal alloys is used when the combination of species desired cannot be evaporated from the same source. Usually there is a large difference in vapor pressure between one component and the other. The vapor pressure of molybdenum (and niobium) is so much lower than that of copper that they cannot be evaporated from the same source. Coevaporation calls for the gas phase mixing of two metal vapors in such a way that the deposit collected is of the desired chemistry. Freestanding foils were produced by coating a smooth substrate having a low coefficient of thermal expansion, a glass microscope slide 25 by 100 mm, and peeling off the coating as a foil after cooling. The foils were approximately 0.05 mm (0.002 in.) thick.

The first few preliminary Cu-Nb deposition cycles were performed at low temperatures. The low temperature coatings, less than 200°C (400°F), were not of very high integrity. Subsequent runs were conducted to investigate variation in the interlayer spacing with higher deposition temperatures. In addition to this variation in the layer spacing, a slight temperature difference was imposed between specimens for each of the deposition cycles. For each cycle, four substrates were coated. Determination of actual process temperature was not achieved because of technical difficulties in

doing so, but it was believed to be about 700° to 800°C (1300° to 1500°F) for the three hotter films produced on each cycle. This temperature range was based on a combination of static thermocouple measurements and radiant heat flux modeling.

The coarsening kinetics of the PVD Cu-15v/oMo were evaluated by means of microhardness values measured as a function of thermal exposure temperature and time. In order to accomplish this, several small samples of the PVD Cu-15v/oMo were sealed under vacuum in quartz tubes. Heat treatments were carried out at 590°, 650° and 700°C (1100°, 1200°, and 1300°F) for times ranging from 0.1 up to 100 hours at each temperature. Upon removal from the furnace, the samples were allowed to cool to room temperature before breaking them out of their capsules.

Upon completion of the thermal exposure cycles, each sample identified with its appropriate time and temperature was prepared for microhardness measurement using standard metallographic procedure. The microhardness measurements were made using Vickers indentation under a 50g load. All values reported were the average of five measurements taken per specimen.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Metallographic specimens were prepared from the as-deposited Cu-15v/oMo on Cu-15v/oNb foils and examined using scanning electron microscopy. The samples that were produced with alternating fluxes of copper and molybdenum or niobium vapor had a uniformly lamellar microstructure. The individual layers were clearly delineated, as shown in Figure 1. The defects apparent in the micrographs are believed to be artifacts from the metallographic preparation.

The codeposited Cu-15v/oMo composite had a very fine microstructure that was difficult to resolve using scanning electron microscopy, as shown in Figure 2. Transmission electron microscopy was used to characterize the material. The as-deposited microstructure was separated into periodic layers of copper and molybdenum, as seen in Figure 3. Apparently during the codeposition of the copper and molybdenum, the elements separated creating a modulated/laminated microstructure in the plane of deposition. The copper interlayers were approximately 25 nm thick. This interlayer

thickness was presumably controlled by the substrate temperature and deposition rate.

The ultimate tensile strength (UTS) of the PVD Cu-15v/oMo and Cu-15v/oNb increased significantly as the copper layer was reduced to less than 1 μm in thickness. The room temperature UTS as a function of copper layer thickness is shown in Figure 4. The ultimate tensile strengths of the codeposited samples are plotted at a layer thickness of 25 nm. It was assumed that the copper layer thickness for the codeposited Cu-15v/oNb samples was similar to that of the codeposited Cu-15v/oMo. The highest strengths were produced with the codeposited Cu-15v/oMo composite. Following the observations made by Spitzig, Pelton, and Laab², the ultimate tensile strengths were plotted proportionally to the inverse square root of the copper layer thickness. The Cu-15v/oMo data were found to correlate well with the Hall-Petch³ relationship, as seen in Figure 5. The Cu-15v/oNb did not agree as well with the Hall-Petch relationship.* The data suggest, however, that the strengths of the PVD materials are controlled by the fineness of the copper interlayers.

The thermal stability of the Cu-15v/oMo composite at elevated temperatures and long times needed to be addressed because the extremely fine structures in these composites are susceptible to coarsening. The fine lamellar interfaces between the copper and molybdenum phases are high surface energy interfaces, which may lead to rapid interfacial diffusion rates. The coarsening kinetics of the codeposited Cu-15v/oMo composite were assessed by measuring the microhardness of coupons that were aged at various times and temperatures. Three exposure temperatures were evaluated: 590°, 650°, and 700°C (1100°, 1200°, and 1300°F). The microhardness results as a function of aging time are shown in Figure 6. The composite initially softened at a rapid rate but decayed to a much slower rate after a few hours at the exposure temperatures. As expected, the highest aging temperature of 700°C (1300°F) resulted in the largest decrease in microhardness. After 100 hours at 700°C (1300°F), the microhardness was 66% of its initial value.

* The layer spacing of 25 nm for the Cu-15v/oNb sample was not measured, but was assumed from the spacing of the Cu-15v/oMo codeposited sample. This may explain the significant deviation of this point from the expected trend line.

The apparent activation energy for coarsening was obtained from an Arrhenius plot of $\log [1/\text{time to microhardness of } 260 \text{ VHN}]$ versus reciprocal of temperature as shown in Figure 7. The apparent activation energy is $229 \pm 84 \text{ kJ/mole}$ ($54.8 \pm 20 \text{ kcal/mole}$). The activation energy for self-diffusion⁴ of molybdenum is reported to range between 385 to 480 kJ/mole (92 to 115 kcal/mole) for temperatures ranging from 1700° to 2200°C (3000° to 4000°F). If the activation energy for interfacial diffusion of molybdenum along the copper/molybdenum interface is comparable to that of grain boundary diffusion, then the activation energy for interfacial diffusion is about half of the activation energy for self-diffusion, i.e., approximately 210 kJ/mole (50 kcal/mole). This suggests that the mechanism of molybdenum layer coarsening is controlled by the interfacial diffusion along the copper/molybdenum interfaces.

The microstructure of the PVD codeposited Cu-15v/oMo after a 1 hour 650°C (1200°F) thermal age is shown in Figure 8. The molybdenum layers have pinched off and agglomerated into discrete molybdenum particle arrays sandwiched between copper layers.

4. CONCLUSIONS

The Cu-15v/oMo and Cu-15v/oNb nanophase composites were produced using electron beam PVD with coevaporation from elemental sources. The foils were produced with i) a codeposited mode in which the vapors of copper and second constituent (molybdenum or niobium) are simultaneously deposited, or ii) alternating layer mode in which the fluxes of copper and second constituent are programmed to be repetitively shuttered. The method produced unique nanoscale layered microstructures. The strength of the nanophase composites were related to the copper interlayer thickness through a Hall-Petch relationship. Microhardness measurements of the Cu-15v/oMo showed that the initial rapid softening rate decayed to a much slower rate after a few hours at temperature. The softening was attributed to the molybdenum layers pinching off and agglomerating into molybdenum islands. The apparent activation energy of 13.1 kJ/mole (54.8 kcal/mole) suggested the molybdenum layer coarsening was controlled by interfacial diffusion of molybdenum. After 100 hours at 700°C (1300°F), the aged microhardness of the Cu-15v/oMo was 66% of the as-deposited microhardness.

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Figure 1. Scanning electron micrograph of cross-sections from (a) Cu-15v/oNb and (b) Cu-15v/oMo composites.

Figure 2. Physical vapor deposited Cu-15v/oMo that was codeposited and in the as-deposited condition. The scanning electron micrograph of cross-section (a) shows the foil was dense with no apparent porosity and (b) a higher magnification micrograph suggesting a laminated morphology.

Figure 3. Transmission electron micrograph of physical vapor deposited Cu-15v/oMo that was codeposited and in the as-deposited condition.

Figure 4. Ultimate tensile strength of physical vapor deposited Cu-15v/oMo and Cu-15v/oNb.

Figure 5. Ultimate tensile strength plotted as a function of the inverse square root of the copper layer thickness.

Figure 6. Microhardness of physical vapor deposited Cu-15v/oMo (codeposited) as a function of aging time for aging temperatures of 590°, 650°, and 700°C (1100°, 1200°, and 1300°F).

Figure 7. Apparent activation energy for microhardness decrease with thermal aging for Cu-15v/oMo.

Figure 8. Transmission electron micrograph of physical vapor deposited Cu-15v/oMo that was codeposited and in the as-deposited condition and after thermal aging at 650°C (1200°F) for 1 hour.